

Methods and Technology of Teaching Russian Foreign Language

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Abstract: The article discusses the main modern methods in teaching Russian as a foreign language and conducts a comparative analysis of them. Some innovative and interactive technologies in teaching Russian as a foreign language are also discussed.

Key words: Russian as a foreign language, teaching methods, teaching technology, teaching, linguistic skills and competencies.

Different peoples of the world have always been interested in learning foreign languages, since it was both a subject of their personal interest and brought them certain benefits in the course of communicating with foreign speakers. The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language is undoubtedly a stable independent pedagogical discipline in which educational and educational functions are the main ones. It establishes patterns that form the basis of educational and cognitive activity aimed at mastering the speech apparatus in Russian [1]. Of course, knowledge and competent use of advanced methods and techniques for teaching Russian as a foreign language helps Russian language teachers to successfully plan and structure the educational process and simplifies the selection of the necessary educational materials.

The scientific community rightly notes that, despite the emergence of electronic education (E-education) using -technologies and distance learning, the central position continues to be occupied by the communicative method [2]. The main thing here is the communicative process itself between a foreign student and a teacher, during which a non-native speaker acquires various language skills. In modern conditions, it is difficult to imagine a communicative method without introducing into its certain regional studies materials and sections that are devoted not only to Russian history and Russian culture, but also to other countries (depending on the audience of listeners).

At the end of the XX - beginning of the XXI century, the topic of intercultural communication and interpenetration of cultures became especially relevant and popular, which is explained by many factors in the development of the modern world. First of all, changes at the global level, the emergence of new actors in world politics, new countries, as well as the simultaneous strengthening of integration processes and the manifestation of disintegration processes in a variety of areas. We agree with the opinion that the method of linguistic and regional studies contributes to the successful acquisition by students from abroad of basic linguistic knowledge, thanks to which they can better understand the traditions and national characteristics of the country of the language they are studying.

Along with communicative methods, it is customary to distinguish conscious-comparative and conscious-practical approaches among the key methods [3]. The first approach is the possibility and use of transfer of skills and competencies from the native language to the target language. The second approach involves the use of language competencies in practical speech activity.

It is important to understand that the use of the latest computer and -technologies in teaching allows foreign students to learn how to effectively and quickly find correct, up-to-date information in Russian, presented on various information platforms, and then effectively use it in official communications.

Creative tasks to create multimedia presentations, which students create and carefully develop, and then present and defend in front of an audience, have wide potential for students' self-development [4]. These projects are an important part of students' independent work.

In the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, the case method is considered successful. This method is associated with the independent thought process of students and represents a solution to a specific situation (case), prepared by a teacher in a certain format and intended for teaching the skills of analyzing different types of information, summarizing it and developing possible solutions, in accordance with established criteria [5]. When using the case method in the process of professional communication, students' intelligence develops. Acting as an interactive method according to its classification and being part of independent work, it helps to increase students' motivation to learn the Russian language. The use of the case method forces foreign students to search for information in different sources and do collective work, that is, it creates professional discussion and discussion. In this context, the preparatory stage and elaboration of a specific case, selection of topics, and definition of goals and objectives on the part of the teacher are very important.

If we talk about innovations in educational technologies, then, first of all, it is also necessary to provide a definition that explains what exactly is included in this concept. According to V.G. Kolosova, "innovative technologies are a set of methods, means and activities that ensure innovative activity." The term "innovative technologies in vocational education" means "technologies focused on the formation of systematic creative technical thinking of students and their ability to generate non-standard technical ideas when solving creative production problems."

Among the variety of technologies, the following can be distinguished:

- learning in collaboration;
- design technologies (project method);
- tandem method;
- case study technology;
- "edutainment" technology,
- distance learning;
- computer teaching technologies;
- Gaming learning technologies, etc.

The use of innovative technologies is possible not only as a way to transfer material to students, organize distance learning of a language, testing, etc., but is also a useful source for the teacher himself. These can be ready-made resources (reference, open educational resources, simulators) or services for developing materials and organizing training (services for creating educational materials, test designer, classroom management, etc.).

Let us consider the work on this topic in more detail. In 2018-2019, defenses were held for candidate dissertations exploring the implementation of innovative technologies in the learning process. I.V. Voronin also considers the possibilities of using electronic educational resources in his work, who proposes to perceive them as special means that allow developing the communicative skills of future teachers when studying multimedia and Internet technologies.

In addition to the direct use of distance education and computer technologies, issues of application and use of specific interactive learning technologies are considered. Thus, in the work of I.O. Amelina talks about "the possibility of combining the didactic potential of media resources and

interactive technologies to enhance the development of relevant competencies of students” and “the creation... of a model... based on the convergence of case technology and media resources, in particular authentic films and television films, as a means training within the framework of the university course of Russian as a foreign language”. In the study by V.M. Filippova examines the linguodidactic potential of the project method and its implementation in teaching Russian as a foreign language “as an effective method of teaching and monitoring the level of development of communicative competence, as well as a means of developing search, creative, practical skills and abilities of a foreign student”.

We can conclude that today there are quite a large number of modern and innovative methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language. This industry is developing in the context of the breakthrough and spread of information and telecommunication technologies and the Internet. This makes the educational process more effective and at the same time more accessible. However, relying only on technological aspects in the educational process does not seem to be the right solution. An integrated approach is required, in which important attention is paid to traditional methods and techniques.

The scientific and pedagogical community agrees that E-education will develop in line with the globalization of education. An example here is the situation with the global pandemic of 2020, when distance learning became an integral part of the educational process. In turn, the effectiveness of distance education will depend on taking into account the personal needs and individual characteristics of students. In the modern period, Russian language teachers face the important task of teaching foreign language students’ professional competencies and skills, since their further competitiveness in the labor market depends on this.

In this regard, it is advisable to use effective, advanced and innovative methods in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language to foreign students. The correct selection and use of modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language affects the motivation of students, which plays a significant role in increasing the effectiveness of teaching Russian as a foreign language in foreign audiences.

Thus, after conducting a review study of materials on the topic “Innovative Technologies”, we can come to the following conclusions:

1. The use of innovative technologies in teaching Russian as a foreign language helps to solve various problems of modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language, in particular, organizing the learning process, creating a language environment, determining the role of the teacher in the classroom, and selecting effective ways to present information.
2. In the process of teaching, both positive and negative aspects of the use of innovative technologies are highlighted.
3. Innovative technologies are numerous and applicable in many fields of knowledge, for different education profiles and levels of training. They play an important role in the system of modern education.
4. Analysis of the materials shows that innovative technologies appear as a means of education for both students and teachers themselves.

The study of these technologies seems relevant, multidimensional and has prospects for further research.

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